

File Sharing System for Mobil Devices Using Data Grid Technology

Sandip Tukaram Shingade¹, Pramila M Chawan²

Computer Engg Department,

VJTI, Mumbai

shingadesandip@gmail.com¹

pmchawan@vjti.org.in²

Abstract

Sharing creates new possibility of entire world and human life, so we are concerned primarily with file exchange and also with direct access to computers, software, data, and other resources. Due to limitation of wireless network in storages space and characteristics their are extraordinary challenges in sharing the files on mobile devices. To solve this problem, we propose architecture to establish file sharing platform for mobile devices, combined with a data grid to help analyze and classify the input.. We propose to implement file download and upload from the client and server get using data grid system can be used for carrying out large scale simulations for medical research and national level distributed database of patient medical records.

Keywords: *Peer-to-Peer Protocol, Short connection time, Standard Generalized Markup Language, Grid Computing, FTP, XML, HTTP.*

1. Introduction

The sharing that we are concerned with is primarily file exchange and also direct access to computers, software, data, and other resources, as is required by a range of collaborative problem solving and resource-brokering strategies emerging in industry, science, and engineering. File sharing is necessarily, highly controlled, with resource providers and consumers defining clearly and carefully just what is shared, who is allowed to share, and the conditions under which sharing occurs. Wireless grids Better use or resources improved energy, power and spectral efficiency. Cooperation and cognition are key principles to be exploited by future wireless networks. We can download a file from the internet to our system, and for sharing the same file we have copy in disk, pen drive to some of our friends. Partially it is very difficult to download

the same file in our mobile due to the wireless network limit, unstable characteristic and restricted storage space, so mobile users face challenges in establishing connections with other users for sharing text, image, video, files.

Here in our proposed system we are uploading as well as downloading a file from the client through server by increasing the speed for sharing by calculating the load of the server nodes. This load of the server nodes will be calculated by the server index, so that the efficiency of the data transfer will be high if the process is assigned to a server with less work load.

We constructed a Grid server to store files, and to provide its computing power for converting various kinds format. Users connect to our servers to select files and download them through Data grid technology.

The remaining of this paper is organized as follows: section 2 explains Different techniques used for sharing files Section 3 explain architecture of wireless grid and file sharing architecture. Section 4 explains the file sharing administrative techniques such as recourses sharing and management of administrative system. Section 5 provides an overview and implementation for telemedicine system and we conclude in section 6.

2. Different techniques used for sharing files.

2.1 Clint to Server: Well known, powerful, reliable server is a data source. Clients request data from server. Very successful model for WWW (HTTP), FTP and Web services. But the limitation of client and server is Scalability is hard to achieve, Presents a single point of failure , Requires administration , Unused resources at the network edge

2.2 Peer-to-Peer Network : Peer to Peer networks is that all clients provides bandwidth, storage space and computing power .Simply it means network of peer node acting as both server and clients For mobile devices it include: a)Short connection time b)Decreased levels of user interaction

2.3 Data Grid: Data Grids are grid computing systems that deal with data. They are built on next-generation computing infrastructures, providing intensive computation and analysis of shared large-scale databases, from hundreds of terabytes to petabytes, across widely distributed scientific communities. We adopted the Globus Toolkit as our Data Grid

Infrastructure. The Data Grid environment provides solutions for security, video and data management, as well as information services. The Globus project use to building grid system and application there is use Globus toolkit is an open source software toolkit. The Globus Toolkit developed within the Globus project provides middleware services for Grid computing environments. Major components include the Grid Security, Infrastructure (GSI), which provides public-key-based authentication and authorization services; resource management services, which provide a language for specifying application requirements, mechanisms for immediate and advance reservations of Grid resources, and for remote job management; and information services.

3. Architecture of Wireless grid.

Wireless grid: cooperative setup of a short-range and cellular (distributed centralized) composite architecture. Wirelessly scalable architecture: The more users, the larger the resource Pool. Target gives Sharing and augmenting resources and capabilities (functionalities) Instead of having one mobile device hosting all functionalities with the best possible quality, the wireless grid uses and shares cleverly the capabilities of several, in principle different, mobile devices

Fig 1. Wireless Grids

3.1 File Sharing Architecture

File sharing system consist of three part;

- 1) **Client Devices:** It will be download as well upload the files using data grid technology

- 2) **Grid Index server:** For client certification it is responsible
- 3) **Grid server node:** It is responsible for handling managing client file and server as client

Fig 2. File Sharing Architecture

4. File sharing Administration and Implementation system

4.1 Management: It consists of three part (1) Information Monitor, (2) Replica Manager, and (3) Data Transfer manager,

Information Monitor: Administrators can monitor the operational status of each machine through the System Information. Monitor being integrated into the Interface Manager. When unusual events occur, the System Information Monitor notifies the Administrator to respond appropriately, thus improving service satisfaction and productivity.

Replica Management: It can create and delete replicas at specified storage sites. A replica manager typically maintains a replica catalog containing replica site addresses and file instances. The Replica Manager periodically synchronizes data lists on all grid servers to ensure data list identical. If the access frequency of some files is high, the Replica Manager will save the files on grid servers, and delete them when access frequency is lower than a given threshold.

Data Transfer Management: It is responsible for data in data-intensive applications. it provides effective and secure transmission for users.

Fig 3. Administration operations

4.2 Resource Sharing:

Resource sharing it gives resource requesters login to the index server through hard wired or wireless network.

User can see resource list database to find resources they want and where to connect to the user who owns the resource, and what other users also downloaded the resource and what other users also downloaded the resource from the server.

Fig 4. Resource sharing operation

5. Case Study of implementation for telemedicine system

Through the telemedicine application is web-based; the client-side application on the mobile is required to effectively mask node failure from the doctor. Besides, the mobile client application also perfected the patient request object before intimating the doctor. This eliminates the waiting time of the doctor thereby improving his efficiency. The composite object consists of the patient request and the treatment profile (patient history). The composite object URL is then sent via SMS / email to the doctor. Servers are used for the web interface while the mobile client application is done using J2ME with MIDP profile. The screenshots of the prototype application using Mobile devices are shown in Fig. The doctor can look at the ECG on his mobile phone and submit his response to the grid. The prescription is updated on the grid and relayed to the patient.

Fig 5. Telemedicine application

6. Conclusion

In this paper we have presented the Grid Technology concept, the recent technology for sharing system for wireless devices integrated with data grid technology. We designed file sharing architecture for wireless grid technology. This paper describe file sharing Administration System in which resource are shared and it all describe management of administrative system research.

7. Reference:

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